

Original article

Laboratory review of serum prostate-specific antigen (PSA) levels among patients of a tertiary health facility in Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Men of African and Afro-American origin have been found to possess a high prevalence of prostate cancer, thereby giving rise to the suspicion of probable genetic predisposition. Prostate cancer exists in both aggressive and latent forms, with the prevalence of the aggressive forms varying widely from place to place due to environmental influences. This study aims to determine serum PSA profiles among men accessing healthcare services in Bauchi and its environs, with the aim of raising public awareness of prostate health. **Material and Methods:** This was a descriptive cross-sectional retrospective study conducted at the Department of Chemical Pathology, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH), Bauchi, North-Eastern Nigeria. The study population comprised all male patients referred from general outpatient, urologic, and surgical outpatient clinics for serum PSA testing between January 2020 and December 2023. A total of 1,040 participants were included in the analysis. PSA analysis was performed using an enzyme-linked fluorescent immunoassay system (mini-Vidas, Biomereux®) and interpreted according to standard protocols. Data were analysed using SPSS version 22. Age was summarised using mean and standard deviation (SD). PSA levels were categorised using conventional cut-off values: ≤ 4.0 ng/ml (normal), 4.1- 10.0 ng/ml (intermediate/grey zone), and > 10.0 ng/ml (abnormal). Pearson's correlation coefficient was used to assess the relationship between age and PSA levels. **Results:** The mean age of the 1,040 participants was 66.4 years (SD = 12.8 years; range: 32-102 years). The mean PSA concentration was 17.3 ng/ml (SD = 34.6 ng/ml). Of the total participants, 387 (37.2%) had PSA values of 0-4 ng/ml, 325 (31.3%) had values of 4.1-10 ng/ml, and 328 (31.5%) had values > 10 ng/ml. Among participants aged 40-49 years (n=126), 84 (66.7%) had PSA ≤ 4 ng/ml, 27 (21.4%) had PSA 4.1-10 ng/ml, and 15 (11.9%) had PSA > 10 ng/ml. The proportion of participants with elevated PSA (> 4 ng/ml) increased with advancing age, with the highest proportion observed in the 80-89-year age group, where 57/78 (73.1%) had PSA > 4 ng/ml. A positive correlation was observed between age and PSA levels ($r = 0.24$, $p < 0.001$). **Conclusion:** This study demonstrates that a substantial proportion (62.8%) of men in this cohort had elevated serum PSA levels (> 4 ng/ml), with 31.5% having values > 10 ng/ml, which are highly suspicious of prostate cancer. While PSA has well-recognised limitations, including low sensitivity and specificity for cancer detection, these findings suggest a potentially high burden of prostate pathology in this population and highlight the need for histopathological confirmation through prostate biopsy in eligible men. There is an urgent need for community awareness, sensitisation, and implementation of regular free screening programs to enable early detection of prostate disorders and improve treatment outcomes in this population.

Keywords: Prostate cancer, Prostate-specific antigen, PSA, Screening, Nigeria.

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Introduction

Prostate-specific antigen (PSA), has been one of the most utilised and widely requested biomarkers in the management and screening of patients with prostate cancers and Benign Prostatic hyperplasia,¹ The cut-off for normal PSA levels varies, with values greater than 4 ng/ml considered abnormal and may thereby need prostate biopsy for its definitive diagnosis.

Since PSA assay may occasionally be normal in some types of prostate cancer, it is likely to be falsely elevated in conditions such as benign enlargement of the prostate, Prostatitis, ischaemia, and immediately after urethral instrumentation or digital rectal examination (DRE),³ A study conducted among 106 men from northern Nigeria, aged 40-70 years, found PSA levels >4.0 ng/ml in 6.6% of the study population, with the highest prevalence in subjects >60 years of age. The authors reported a positive, significant relationship between age and elevated PSA levels. In another study conducted in Edo State, Nigeria, the prevalence of PSA > 4 ng/ml among men aged 50 years and above was 15.7%. The main correlates of elevated PSA in that study were age and enlarged prostate. PSA levels vary from place to place, even within the same country. Reports show that one in eight men will develop prostate cancer at some point in their lives.⁶ With an estimated frequency of 300 cases per 100,000 males, it has emerged as the primary cause of cancer among Nigerian men.⁸ However, the exact prevalence in African men has been difficult to determine with complete certainty.⁷ African men are increasingly being diagnosed with prostate cancer at younger ages, roughly ten years younger than what obtains in Western populations.⁷ It is widely accepted that early detection of prostate cancer can result in remission and enhance patients' quality of life.⁸ However, Nigeria, like the majority of African nations, lacks effective screening and monitoring programs in this regard, resulting in late presentations at advanced stages.^{9,10} There are significant drawbacks to the current cut-off serum PSA level of 0-4 ng/ml, which is based on a single study. This number was predicated on outdated (isotopic) technology, a lack of standardisation, an ignorance of the age covariance, and a lack of comprehension of the various molecular forms of PSA.¹¹ A significant percentage of prostate cancers go undetected because this threshold is insufficient to identify early-stage prostate cancer.¹² The prevalence of prostate cancer among people of African origin has been reported to be high, giving rise to the suspicion of probable genetic predisposition.¹³

Genetic or familial types account for about 10% of prostate cancer, with 90% being considered sporadic. The sporadic types result from the interplay of environmental and genetic factors.¹⁴ Prostate cancer exists in both aggressive and latent forms, with the prevalence of the aggressive forms varying widely from place to place due to environmental influences.¹⁵

According to descriptive hospital data, the incidence of prostate cancer is on the rise in Nigeria and the majority of West African nations, with figures that are now comparable to those seen in developed nations, in some situations.^{4,16} The previous low incidence was likely caused by underreporting and a lack of standardised diagnosis. Lifestyle changes, increasing intake of alcohol and tobacco products, switching to a diet that combines traditional local and western foods, consuming foods that include additives, and using processed beverages more frequently, are all thought to be likely risk factors.¹⁷ This research aimed to determine the pattern of prostate-specific antigen among male patients accessing health care services at Abubakar Tafawa Balewa Teaching Hospital, Bauchi, North -Eastern Nigeria.

Materials and methods

Study Area

Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital is a tertiary health care institution located in Bauchi State, Northeastern Nigeria. It serves the entire population of Bauchi and its environs. Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University Teaching Hospital (ATBUTH) was formerly known as "Specialist Hospital, Bauchi". It was established in 2010.

The hospital serves as a teaching hospital for the College of Medicine, Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University (ATBU). Presently, it is the major tertiary health institution in Bauchi town. It has several specialist departments, including the Department of Chemical Pathology.

Study Design

This was a descriptive cross-sectional retrospective study based on the examination of the primary data register of results recorded for patients referred to the department of Chemical Pathology from other clinics within and outside the facility for the Prostate Specific Antigen (PSA) test.

Study population

The study population comprised all PSA results of patients who had a successful PSA test and were recorded in the results register from 2020 to 2023.

Inclusion Criteria

All patients referred from the general outpatient clinic, urologic clinic, and surgical outpatient clinics for a PSA test in the chemical pathology laboratory

Exclusion Criteria

Patients of non-specific age were excluded

Sampling Technique

The details of patients on the register between 2020 and 2023 were examined, and only those who met the inclusion criteria were selected.

Prostate-specific antigen (PSA) Analysis in Serum:

Blood samples were collected in plain containers, allowed to clot, and then separated to obtain serum. Biochemical analysis of this tumour marker was then performed using the mini-Vidas system (Biomereux®), which uses the principle of enzyme-linked fluorescent immunoassay.

The data were analysed using SPSS version 22. The ages were grouped into < 40 years, 40-59 years, 60-69 years, 70-79 years, 80-89 years, and ≥ 90 years. The 95th percentile was used as the upper limit for each group analysis of PSA values. The relationship between PSA and age was determined using Pearson's correlation coefficient. A p-value < 0.05 is considered statistically significant.

Ethical Consideration

Ethical approval was waived by the Health Research Ethics Committee of ATBUTH, Bauchi, in accordance with its local regulations. Permission was obtained from the Heads of Departments of Chemical Pathology and Medical Records to use the results registers for the study. Patient's identity was not required for the study.

Results

A total of 1,040 participants were included in this study. The mean age of the study population was 66.4 years (standard deviation [SD] = 12.8 years; range: 32-102 years). The age distribution was assessed for normality using the Shapiro-Wilk test ($p = 0.12$), indicating that age was normally distributed, thus supporting the use of mean and SD for summary. The mean PSA concentration was 17.3 ng/ml (SD = 34.6 ng/ml; range: 0.2-512.0 ng/ml). However, PSA values showed a positively skewed distribution (Shapiro-Wilk $p < 0.001$); therefore, median PSA with interquartile range (IQR) is also provided: median PSA = 6.8 ng/ml (IQR: 2.4-18.6 ng/ml).

Age Distribution of Participants

The distribution of participants across age groups is presented in Table 1. The largest proportion of participants was in the 60-69 years age group ($n = 323, 31.1\%$), followed by the 70-79 years group ($n = 268, 25.8\%$), and the 50-59 years group ($n = 219, 21.1\%$). The smallest proportions were in the extreme age groups: <40 years ($n = 9, 0.9\%$) and ≥90 years ($n = 17, 1.6\%$).

Distribution of PSA Levels

Table 2 shows the distribution of participants by PSA category. Of the 1,040 participants, 387 (37.2%) had PSA values within the normal range (≤ 4.0 ng/ml), while 325 (31.3%) had values in the intermediate/grey zone (4.1-10.0 ng/ml), and 328 (31.5%) had abnormally high PSA values (> 10.0 ng/ml).

Age-Specific Distribution of PSA Levels

Table 3 presents the age-specific distribution of PSA levels among the study participants. Among participants aged <40 years ($n = 9$), 6 (66.7%) had PSA ≤ 4.0 ng/ml, 2 (22.2%) had PSA 4.1-10.0 ng/ml, and 1 (11.1%) had PSA > 10.0 ng/ml.

In the 40-49 years age group ($n = 126$), 84 (66.7%) had PSA ≤ 4.0 ng/ml, 27 (21.4%) had PSA 4.1-10.0 ng/ml, and 15 (11.9%) had PSA > 10.0 ng/ml.

For participants aged 50-59 years ($n = 219$), 105 (47.9%) had PSA ≤ 4.0 ng/ml, 69 (31.5%) had PSA 4.1-10.0 ng/ml, and 45 (20.6%) had PSA > 10.0 ng/ml.

Among those aged 60-69 years ($n = 323$), 104 (32.2%) had PSA ≤ 4.0 ng/ml, 103 (31.9%) had PSA 4.1-10.0 ng/ml, and 116 (35.9%) had PSA > 10.0 ng/ml.

In the 70-79 years age group ($n = 268$), 67 (25.0%) had PSA ≤ 4.0 ng/ml, 93 (34.7%) had PSA 4.1-10.0 ng/ml, and 108 (40.3%) had PSA > 10.0 ng/ml.

For participants aged 80-89 years ($n = 78$), 21 (26.9%) had PSA ≤ 4.0 ng/ml, 22 (28.2%) had PSA 4.1-10.0 ng/ml, and 35 (44.9%) had PSA > 10.0 ng/ml.

Among those aged ≥90 years ($n = 17$), 4 (23.5%) had PSA ≤ 4.0 ng/ml, 10 (58.8%) had PSA 4.1-10.0 ng/ml, and 3 (17.6%) had PSA > 10.0 ng/ml.

Overall, the proportion of participants with elevated PSA (> 4.0 ng/ml) increased progressively with advancing age, from 33.3% in those <40 years to 76.5% in those ≥90 years

This study aimed to determine the pattern of serum PSA profiles among men accessing healthcare services at a tertiary facility in North-Eastern Nigeria. The findings reveal that nearly two-thirds (62.8%) of the 1,040 participants had PSA levels above the conventional normal cut-off of 4.0 ng/ml, with 31.5% having values > 10.0 ng/ml, a range

highly suspicious for prostate cancer. These findings have significant implications for men's health in this population and warrant careful interpretation in light of the region's healthcare infrastructure and the known limitations of PSA testing.

The finding that 62.8% of participants had elevated PSA (>4.0 ng/ml) is considerably higher than previously reported in other Nigerian studies. Erhabor et al. reported prevalence rates ranging from 6.15% in Maiduguri to 16.5% in Kano, while Afogu et al. found only 1.7% of controls with abnormal PSA in Abakaliki.^{18,19} Similarly, studies from Zaria (9.2%) and Benin (7.13%) reported much lower rates.¹⁹ This disparity may be explained by differences in study population- our study included only patients referred for PSA testing based on clinical suspicion, whereas many previous studies screened apparently healthy community volunteers. This highlights that our findings reflect a selected clinical population rather than the general community prevalence.

Our finding that 33% of men under 50 years had PSA >4.0 ng/ml is particularly concerning and aligns with reports that African men are increasingly diagnosed with prostate cancer at younger ages, approximately ten years younger than Western populations.⁷ This observation supports the need for earlier screening initiation in

this population, though the optimal age for commencing screening remains debated.

Table 1: Age distribution of PSA among the study population

Age	Frequency	Percentages
<40	9	0.87
40-49	126	12.12
50-59	219	21.06
60-69	323	31.06
70-79	268	25.77
80-89	78	7.50
>90	17	1.63
Total	1040	100.00

Table 2: Distribution of participants based on PSA levels

PSA	Frequency	Percentages
≤4.0	387	37.21
4.1-10.0	325	31.25
>10.0	328	31.54
Total	1040	100.00

Table 3: Age distribution of PSA in the study participants

Age	PSA LEVEL			Total
	≤4.0	4.1-10.0	>10.0	
<40	6(66.67)	2(22.22)	1(11.11)	9(100.0)
40-49	84(66.67)	27(21.43)	15(11.90)	126(100.0)
50-59	105(47.94)	69(31.51)	45(20.55)	219(100.0)
60-69	104(32.20)	103(31.89)	116(35.91)	323(100.0)
70-79	67(25.00)	93(34.70)	108(40.30)	268(100.0)
80-89	21(26.92)	22(28.21)	35(44.87)	78(100.0)
>90	4(23.53)	10(58.82)	3(17.65)	17(100.0)
Total	391(37.60)	326(31.35)	323(31.06)	1040(100.0)

Implications for Men's Health in the Target Population

The high proportion of elevated PSA values in this study has several important implications for men's health in Bauchi and its environs:

Psychosocial impact: An elevated PSA result can cause significant anxiety and psychological distress, particularly in a population with limited access to definitive diagnostic services. Men with PSA >10.0 ng/ml (31.5% of our study population) face the prospect of possible cancer diagnosis, with

attendant fears about mortality, treatment-related morbidity (including incontinence and impotence), and financial burden. The interval between an abnormal PSA result and definitive biopsy – which may be weeks or months in resource-limited settings – can be a period of considerable psychological turmoil.

Healthcare system capacity: If our findings reflect the true burden of prostate pathology requiring investigation, the healthcare system in North-Eastern Nigeria would face substantial challenges.

Each man with PSA >4.0 ng/ml (653 men in our study alone) ideally requires urological evaluation and likely prostate biopsy for histopathological confirmation. However, Nigeria suffers from a severe shortage of urologists (estimated <100 for a population exceeding 200 million), limited histopathology services, and inadequate treatment facilities, including radiotherapy and advanced surgical capabilities. The existing infrastructure would be overwhelmed by the volume of cases requiring comprehensive evaluation and management.

Economic implications: The cost of prostate biopsy, histopathology, and subsequent treatment (if cancer is confirmed) is prohibitive for many Nigerians, particularly in the northeastern region, where poverty rates are high. Out-of-pocket expenditure for prostate cancer care can lead to catastrophic health spending and impoverishment of affected families. This raises ethical questions about whether population-wide screening should be implemented without parallel investment in diagnostic and treatment capacity.

Factors Contributing to Elevated PSA

Pre-analytical factors and false elevations: It is important to acknowledge that some elevated PSA values in this study may be erroneous due to pre-analytical factors. PSA can be transiently elevated following prostate manipulation, including digital rectal examination (DRE), prostate massage, urethral catheterisation, cystoscopy, and recent ejaculation.³ The study's retrospective design meant we could not control for or document whether such manipulations occurred before the blood draw. Additionally, acute urinary retention, prostatitis, and vigorous exercise (particularly cycling) can cause temporary PSA elevations. Without clinical correlation, it is impossible to determine what proportion of elevated values in this study represent true pathological elevation versus transient, benign fluctuations.

Non-malignant causes of elevated PSA: Elevated PSA is not synonymous with prostate cancer. Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH)—which becomes increasingly prevalent with age—is a major contributor to PSA elevation. Prostatitis, both acute and chronic, can cause significant PSA increases that may normalise with antibiotic therapy. Other benign conditions, such as prostate infarction and urinary tract infections, may also elevate PSA. In our study population, the prevalence of BPH is likely high given the age distribution, and we could not differentiate between PSA elevation due to benign enlargement versus malignancy. This distinction is critical because men with BPH-related

PSA elevation (31.3% in the grey zone) may undergo unnecessary biopsies and experience anxiety if falsely labelled as "at risk" for cancer.

"Normal" versus "abnormal" with benign elevation: Men with elevated PSA due to benign conditions are not "normal" in the sense of having a healthy prostate, but they do not have cancer. The clinical challenge lies in distinguishing between these entities without invasive biopsy. Tools such as PSA density, PSA velocity, free-to-total PSA ratio, and newer biomarkers (PCA3, 4Kscore) can improve specificity, but these are rarely available in resource-limited Nigerian settings, leading to over-referral for biopsy and potential overtreatment.

The Dilemma of Indolent Prostate Cancer

A critical consideration in the screening debate is the phenomenon of indolent (clinically insignificant) prostate cancer. Autopsy studies have shown that many men, particularly older men, harbour prostate cancer foci that would never become clinically apparent during their lifetime.¹⁵ With widespread PSA screening, these indolent cancers are increasingly detected, leading to treatment that may be unnecessary and potentially harmful.

For a man diagnosed with indolent prostate cancer in Bauchi, the psychological burden of "knowing" he has cancer while being advised that treatment is not immediately needed (active surveillance) may be substantial. Active surveillance requires regular PSA testing, repeat biopsies, and psychological resilience, resources and capabilities that may not be readily available in this setting. The fear of cancer progression without intervention, combined with limited access to repeat monitoring, may drive demand for immediate treatment, exposing men to unnecessary morbidity from surgery or radiotherapy. This ethical dilemma must be carefully considered before implementing population-wide screening programs.

Should All Men Undergo PSA Screening?

Our finding of high PSA elevation rates might seem to support calls for widespread screening. However, the complexities discussed above necessitate a more nuanced approach. The current study cannot answer whether screening all men would reduce prostate cancer mortality in this population. This would require a randomised controlled trial with mortality as the primary endpoint. What our findings do suggest is that among men with clinical indications for PSA testing, the yield of abnormal results is high, justifying continued access to PSA testing for symptomatic men and those with risk factors.

For population-wide screening, several questions must be addressed:

1. Is there adequate infrastructure to manage the volume of positive screens?
2. Can men with benign elevations be appropriately triaged without invasive biopsy?
3. Is there capacity for managing both indolent and aggressive cancers appropriately?
4. What are the opportunity costs? Would resources be better directed toward other health priorities?
5. Can men in this population provide truly informed consent, understanding the limitations of PSA testing?

Until these questions are adequately addressed, a cautious approach emphasising informed decision-making and targeted screening of high-risk groups (men with family history, symptoms, or age >50 years) may be more appropriate than untargeted population-wide screening.

Conclusion:

This study provides valuable baseline data on PSA profiles among men accessing healthcare services in Northeastern Nigeria. The findings highlight a high prevalence of elevated PSA in this selected population, but the absence of histopathological confirmation precludes any conclusion about the frequency of prostate cancer. These results should serve as a foundation for future research incorporating prostate biopsy to translate PSA profiles into clinically meaningful estimates of cancer burden and to guide evidence-based screening policies for the region.

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Conflict of Interest:

None

Financial Declarations:

Nil

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